

How to make open scholarly data beneficial to science *and* journalism? A generative dataset on Covid-19 preprints

Steffen Lemke, Meik Bittkowski, Hristio Boytchev, and Isabella Peters

Several studies on how researchers published and how non-scientific audiences processed scientific findings during the Covid-19 pandemic suggest that the system of science communication changed profoundly during this global crisis (Watson, 2022). One such change concerns an observed ascent of preprints as a publication format to swiftly distribute novel findings. By the end of April 2020, already almost 7,000 Covid-19-related preprints had been published on preprint servers, accounting for 35% of all scientific Covid-19-related publications (Fraser et al., 2021). Moreover, during the Covid-19 crisis a surge of preprint use within journalistic reporting could be seen (Fleerackers et al., 2022). Their typically unreviewed and preliminary nature poses particular challenges to outer-academic readers of preprints, who might not be aware of their particular potential degree of uncertainty.

Within our project we follow the goal of developing a comprehensive and informative dataset of preprints related to Covid-19. With this dataset, we aim to support three primary user groups in comprehending the mass of preprinted Covid-19 literature: scientometric researchers, medical experts, and journalists. We seek to provide informative publication-level metadata, which shall enable detailed classifications of individual preprints, assist stakeholders like journalists in their relevance assessments, and lay a foundation for future scientometric analyses of the preprint-based science communication during the pandemic.

Structurally, the dataset consists of multiple layers fulfilling different information needs: the basic layer consists of publication metadata, e.g., titles, abstracts, article identifiers, impact indicators, affiliated authors and organizations, or subject field classifications. A second layer consists of author networks, which shall help to reveal connections between collaborating groups. A third layer consists of preprints' full texts, which enable numerous applications within natural language processing. A fourth layer includes document embeddings based on the preprints' titles and abstracts, to allow for fine-grained classifications of preprints in relation to each other, while a fifth layer captures citation intents within respective articles.

Technically, we provide our data as a generative dataset. I.e., the dataset is organized as a set of computational notebooks that users can run to reconstruct the parts of the dataset they are interested in. An advantage of this generative design is that it allows for the inclusion of data from sources whose licensing terms would otherwise prohibit to pass it on as a download (in our dataset this for instance concerns data from *Digital Science's Dimensions*). Also, it allows large parts of our software to work as a generic pipeline for publication data in general. A disadvantage is that a larger amount of effort is required from the dataset's users, who need to exert a basic understanding of programming, and for certain parts of the data acquire their own access credentials (e.g., a Dimensions API key).

While we are interested in feedback to the dataset's contents and potential improvements, we also consider our contribution a stimulus to discussing promising approaches of how to ideally share open scholarly datasets with stakeholders from diverse professional backgrounds. Our dataset serves as an example of how data from heterogeneous open data sources can be aggregated and made available to larger audiences – a task that we deem likely to become even more relevant for the various stakeholder groups concerned with science communication in the future.

References

- Fleerackers, A., Riedlinger, M., Moorhead, L., Ahmed, R., & Alperin, J. P. (2022). Communicating Scientific Uncertainty in an Age of COVID-19: An Investigation into the Use of Preprints by Digital Media Outlets. *Health Communication*, 37(6), 726–738. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10410236.2020.1864892>
- Fraser, N., Brierley, L., Dey, G., Polka, J. K., Pálffy, M., Nanni, F., & Coates, J. A. (2021). The evolving role of preprints in the dissemination of COVID-19 research and their impact on the science communication landscape. *PLOS Biology*, 19(4), e3000959. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3000959>
- Watson, C. (2022). Rise of the preprint: How rapid data sharing during COVID-19 has changed science forever. *Nature Medicine*, 28(1), Art. 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-021-01654-6>

Corresponding author's short CV

Steffen Lemke works as a postdoctoral researcher at Kiel University's Department for Computer Science, where he is a member of the Web Science Group under supervision of Prof. Dr. Isabella Peters. After obtaining a master's degree in information systems at Kiel University in 2016, Steffen started as a research assistant and PhD candidate at ZBW – Leibniz Information Centre for Economics, where he worked in several projects funded by the DFG and the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research. In 2022, Steffen obtained a doctoral degree in computer science at Kiel University for his thesis titled *An Assessment of Impact Metrics' Potential as Research Indicators Based on Their Perception, Usage, and Dependencies from External Science Communication*.

Steffen's research is mainly located within the domains of scientometrics and information science. His primary research interests are scholarly metrics (with a focus on altmetrics), science communication, and interdependencies between the spheres of science journalism and research assessment.